

METHOD ON FORMATION 4-C SKILLS

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Abstract. *In the given article the method on formation 4-C skills critical thinking, communication, collaboration and creativity in modern education is discussed. The analysis of strategies and approaches to the development of these competencies among students is presented. Key aspects of the methodology are discussed, including the use of technology, adaptability, self-regulation, whole person learning, continuous learning and self-development, interdisciplinarity, stimulation of creative thinking, and assessment and feedback. The article highlights the importance of a systematic approach to building 4-C skills to adapt successfully students to a rapidly changing environment and prepare them for future challenges and opportunities.*

Keywords: *4-C skills, critical thinking, communication, collaboration, creativity, education, methodology, technology, adaptability, self-regulation, interdisciplinarity, creative thinking, assessment, feedback, learning process, self-development.*

Introduction. In information society of present time, saturated with technological innovation and rapid change, learning is not limited to the simple transfer of knowledge. It is designed to develop in students a set of skills that will allow them to successfully cope with the challenges of the modern world. One of the key concepts in this context are the 4-C skills: critical thinking, communication, collaboration and creativity.

It is not a secret that the introduction of methods for developing these skills becomes an integral part of the educational process, aimed at preparing students for successful adaptation in a dynamic world. This technique involves not only the transfer of information, but also the active involvement of students in the learning process, developing their skills to think critically, communicate effectively, collaborate and show a creative approach to solving problems.

Definitely, this introduction will review the basic principles and strategies of the 4-C Skills Framework and its implications for modern education and future student success. Particular attention will be paid to the importance of these skills in the context of rapid technological development and the global challenges facing modern societies.

4-C skills are a set of skills needed in today's world, which is rapidly changing due to technological progress. This term refers to four main categories of skills: Critical Thinking, Communication, Collaboration and Creativity. The methodology for the formation of these skills includes a number of strategies and approaches aimed at developing the competencies necessary for successful adaptation to a rapidly changing environment.

1. Critical thinking:

- **Analysis and evaluation of information:** Learning how to analyze information from different sources, as well as developing the skills to critically evaluate this information, taking into account its reliability, relevance and significance.

- **Solution of the Problem:** Support students to develop skills in finding alternative solutions, identifying the causes of problems and applying strategies to solve them.

- **Decision Making:** Learning to make informed decisions based on the analysis of facts and data.

2. **Communication:**

- **Oral and Written Communication:** Developing the ability to express thoughts and ideas, both orally and written and to interact effectively with others.

- **Listening and Understanding:** Learn the skills of active listening and empathic understanding of other people's points of view.

- **Intercultural Communication:** Prepare to interact with people from different cultures and develop respect for diversity.

3. **Cooperation:**

- **Teamwork:** Learning how to collaborate effectively with colleagues, including sharing responsibilities, resolving conflicts and achieving common goals.

- **Group dynamics:** Understanding of the principles and characteristics of working in a group, including the ability to be a leader and follower depending on the situation.

- **Interdependence and Collaboration:** Developing the skills that are important to interact successfully with different stakeholders, including delegation, accepting feedback and supporting other team members.

4. **Creativity:**

- **Generation of Ideas:** The ability to generate new ideas and approaches to solving problems and to see opportunities where others might miss them.

- **Innovative thinking:** Developing the ability to think innovatively and find innovative solutions to complex problems.

- **Experiment and Risk:** Support students to experiment and take risks as they search for new ideas and solutions.

Effective method of formation 4-C skills involves actively engaging students in a variety of learning scenarios that encourage the development of these competencies through hands-on activities, brainstorming and reflection. In addition, it is important to provide faculty support and create a stimulating learning environment that encourages creativity, collaboration, and critical thinking.

5. **Use of technology:**

- **Digital Literacy:** Training students with the basics of using a variety of digital tools and technologies and developing skills in searching, evaluating and using information from the Internet.

- **Technological Creativity:** Promoting the development of skills in creating and applying new technological solutions in order to solve problems and achieve goals.

6. **Adaptability and flexibility:**

- **Change Management:** Learning to adapt for changes and respond effectively to unexpected circumstances.

- **Developing self-confidence:** Supporting students to develop self-confidence and the ability to adapt to different situations.

7. **Self-regulation and self-organization:**

- **Planning and time management:** Developing skills in drawing up action plans and managing time effectively to achieve set goals.

- Self-monitoring and assessment: Teaching students the skills of self-monitoring and self-assessment of the results of their activities for the purpose of continuous improvement.

8. Training of the whole person:

- Developing emotional intelligence: Supporting students to develop emotional literacy, the ability to manage their emotions and empathy for others.

- Physical and Spiritual Well-Being: Emphasize the physical health and spiritual development of students as important aspects of overall personal development.

The effective method for the formation of 4-C skills requires a systematic approach, including both educational practices in the educational process and the creation of a favorable educational environment in schools and educational institutions. This allows us to ensure the comprehensive development of students and prepare them for successful adaptation and professional growth in the modern world.

9. Lifelong learning and self-development:

- Commitment to learning: Supporting students to develop habits of lifelong learning and self-development, emphasizing the importance of lifelong learning in the modern world.

- Developing Learning Strategies: Teaching effective learning and information retrieval strategies for productive acquisition of knowledge and skills.

10. Interdisciplinarity:

- Cross-Disciplinary Connections: Promoting understanding of the relationships between different subject areas and develop the ability to apply knowledge from different fields to solve complex problems.

- Developing Flexible Thinking: Supporting the development of flexible thinking and the ability to rethink problems through multiple perspectives.

11. Stimulating creative thinking:

- Creating a suitable learning environment: Creating a learning environment that stimulates creative thinking, including the use of interactive teaching methods and stimulating tasks.

- Supporting the idea of initiative: Encouraging students to take initiative and independently search for innovative solutions.

12. Assessment and feedback:

- Formative Assessment: Using formative assessment methods to monitor continuously students' progress and tailor the educational process to their needs.

- Feedback: Providing structured and constructive feedback to support skill development and address weaknesses.

The effective method for the formation of 4-C skills requires constant development and improvement in accordance with the changing requirements of modern society and the labor market. The introduction of such methodology allows students not only to acquire successfully knowledge, but also develop the skills necessary for their future professional and personal growth.

Conclusion:

By concluding the ideas mentioned above it can be suggested that the article presents a methodology for the formation of 4-C skills in modern education, which is a key aspect of preparing students for the requirements of modern society and the labor market. The strategies and approaches discussed, including the emphasis on critical thinking, communication, collaboration and creativity, emphasize the importance of holistic personal development. The implementation of the proposed methodology will ensure that students not only successfully master knowledge,

but also develop the skills necessary for their future success and adaptation to a rapidly changing world.

Developing 4-C skills not only improves students' chances of successfully integrating into modern society, but also helps develop a deep understanding and critical view of the world around them. The methodology presented in the article focuses on the integrated approach to education, including the use of modern technologies, stimulation of creative thinking and the development of emotional intelligence. The application of this methodology in teaching practice will help to create a learning environment that promotes active participation of students in the learning process and develop student's full potential.

REFERENCES

1. Miller, K. (2020). *Communication theories: Perspectives, processes, and contexts*. McGraw-Hill Education.
2. Griffin, E. (2019). *A first look at communication theory*. McGraw-Hill Education.
3. Littlejohn, S. W., & Foss, K. A. (2017). *Theories of human communication*. Waveland Press.
4. Darling-Hammond, L. (2017). Teacher education around the world: What can we learn from international practice? *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 40(3), 291-309.
5. Hattie, J. (2012). *Visible learning for teachers: Maximizing impact on learning*. Routledge.
6. Gardner, H. (2011). *Frames of mind: The theory of multiple intelligences*. Basic Books.